

Project Title	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice
Project Acronym	WorldFAIR
Grant Agreement No	101058393
Instrument	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01
Topic, type of action	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months
Project Website	http://worldfair-project.eu

M5: WorldFAIR Communication Toolkit

Work Package	WP14
Lead Author (Org)	Alexandra Delipalta (RDA Association)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	-
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Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

M5: WorldFAIR Communication Toolkit

Building on the project identity which was developed as part of Milestone 2, the Communication Toolkit will be continuously updated throughout the project as new materials and collaterals are developed for various purposes; the communication toolkit will be maintained and shared at:

- WorldFAIR website (main): <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit>
- Research Data Alliance website: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe>¹
- CODATA website: <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/>

Table 1 below outlines the materials that have been developed or are currently in progress (available at the links above):

¹ Please note that the Research Data Alliance website is currently being revised; as a result this URL may change.

Table 1. WorldFAIR Communication Toolkit

Material	Description	Status
Information Box for presentations	One slide to be used at every presentation related to WorldFAIR outputs linking to the project.	Completed
Acknowledgement for publications	The following attribution is to be used in all project outputs: "This work was developed as part of the 'Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice' (WorldFAIR), funded by the EC HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 Coordination and Support Action under Grant Agreement No. 101058393. We acknowledge the support provided by the project partners and resources".	Completed
Branded roll-up banner	A roll-up banner to be used at events where WorldFAIR partners participate and/or present project activities / outputs	In progress, to be completed by January 2023.
Reusable branded poster template	A PowerPoint poster template with project branding to be used for all project poster presentations	Completed
Branded flyer - template	A reusable template for flyers to be used where WorldFAIR partners participate in events and to be adapted based on promotional needs	In progress, to be completed by Jan 2023.
Zenodo community	https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project/	Completed, managed by the WP1 project coordination

Material	Description	Status
		team
Collection of collaterals	A collection of marketing collaterals developed throughout the project lifetime.	In progress throughout the project
Collection of press releases	A collection of press releases published throughout the project lifetime.	In progress throughout the project
Collection of newsletters	A collection of all newsletters issued throughout the project lifetime.	In progress throughout the project
Collection of presentations	A collection of all presentations delivered at events by project partners and case studies on project outputs.	In progress throughout the project
Website	Project website to store and disseminate project results and plans: https://worldfair-project.eu/	Completed